

methods were compared using a sample of more than 3,000 traditional varieties. The classification coincided in 99% of the cases. In the other 1%, rices fell into one group in one case and were

classified intermediaries in the other case.

A similar finding was observed among modern varieties produced by hybridization within a group. Of 87 varieties whose parentage involves at

least 2 different groups, only 4 (5%) gave different results using the 2 methods.

The simplified method is highly reliable. It is fast, cheap, and requires no sophisticated equipment. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Ratooning ability of IR varieties in Hangzhou, China

Qiu Baiqin and Jin Qingsheng, Crop Institute, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Hangzhou, China

We evaluated 28 IR varieties, from IR5 to IR64, for ratooning ability. Pregerminated seeds were sown on 18 Apr 1986 in a screenhouse and 8 plants of each variety were transplanted on 17 May at 20- × 15-cm spacing. At maturity, plants were cut to 15-cm height and scored for ratooning ability 15 d after cutting.

IR29, IR30, IR43, and IR64 had relatively high ratooning ability; ratoon crops yielded about 50% of main crops (see table). In 13 varieties, ratooning was intermediate; ratoon crops yielded 20-30% of main crops. In seven varieties, the ratoon crops did not head because of the long growth duration of the main crop and subsequent low temperatures during the ratoon crop. Main crop and ratoon crop growth durations and yields did not correlate. □

Average duration and grain yield of IR varieties in main crop and ratoon crop. Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Variety	Main crop		Ratoon crop		Ratoon scale
	Maturity (d)	Yield (g/plant)	Maturity (d)	Yield (g/plant)	
IR5	171	14.9	—	—	—
IR8	167	15.7	—	—	—
IR20	164	14.6	—	—	—
IR22	145	14.5	48	4.2	5
IR24	123	16.5	56	4.5	5
IR26	126	13.1	46	3.8	5
IR28	111	16.2	52	1.8	9
IR29	118	11.7	47	5.8	1
IR30	119	12.4	50	6.4	1
IR32	172	14.4	—	—	—
IR34	148	16.3	44	3.8	5
IR36	120	15.7	48	4.1	5
IR38	134	12.6	50	2.4	5
IR40	155	12.8	—	—	—
IR42	164	11.7	—	—	—
IR43	135	12.3	42	6.0	1
IR44	131	11.4	49	2.7	5
IR45	141	11.9	51	3.3	5
IR46	151	13.0	41	2.6	5
IR48	167	11.6	—	—	—
IR50	114	11.9	50	1.5	9
IR52	130	11.6	54	2.9	5
IR54	133	13.0	57	3.0	5
IR56	119	14.8	43	2.9	5
IR58	110	12.1	42	1.7	9
IR60	120	12.9	41	1.4	9
IR62	143	13.8	45	2.6	5
IR64	126	12.5	51	6.1	1

Performance of CR666 rice cultures

G.A. Palanisamy, K. Natarajamoorthy, and S. Palanisamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, India

To identify a very short-duration variety that can fit into the 60-d fallow between 2 turmeric crops in Kalingarayan canal tract, we tested 5 promising lines of CR666. The entries were direct seeded on 16 Jul 86 in a randomized block design replicated three times. Because no local variety is in the 60-d duration

Performance of CR666 lines at Coimbatore, India, 1986.

Line	Duration (d)	Mean plant ht (cm)	Mean tillers/plant	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
CR666-14	75	68	6	17	1.3
CR666-18	74	71	8	17	1.9
CR666-36-4	75	66	6	16	0.8
CR666-37-38	73	87	6	21	1.5
CR666-119	75	65	7	17	0.9

group, a local check could not be included.

The 5 lines, which reportedly mature in 60 d at Cuttack, took about 15 d longer at Coimbatore, perhaps because

of the difference in latitude and elevation. Cuttack is situated 20° 30'N at 23 m, Coimbatore at 11° 02'N at 431 m. CR666-18 gave the maximum yield, followed by CR666-37-38 (see table). □